

PRODUCT DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT FOR CHEMICAL ENGINEERING: ISSUES AND CHALLENGES

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ABSTRACT

This paper details the curriculum revamp effort aimed at improving design-build experience for Diploma in Chemical Engineering students at Singapore Polytechnic. It describes how chemical product engineering is being introduced into the curriculum to provide students with an integrated coverage of skills in conceiving, designing, implementing and operating an engineering system using chemical engineering principles across the three years of study.

The paper first explains the challenges faced during the execution of final year (capstone) projects, for which all graduating Year 3 students must complete. The existing curriculum lacked a consistent approach that facilitate students in conceiving viable engineering product or system by applying various chemical engineering principles learnt over the years. Also discussed is the mismatch between the aims of an institutional module (i.e. module to be subscribed by all diplomas) to equip students with an understanding of design process with applications in chemical engineering.

It then explores the emergence of chemical product engineering, and described how we integrate this “third paradigm” of chemical engineering into our curriculum. A brief literature review is presented, and the scope of coverage at diploma level is discussed. We introduced a Year 2 module *Product Design and Development* that provides a systematic coverage of chemical product design; and briefly discuss changes made to the assessment of Year 3 *Final Year Project* to better reflect different learning outcome inherent in different projects genres. Feedback obtained from student surveys was also discussed: Year 2 students on their learning experience with *Product Design and Development*, and Year 3 students on difficulties and challenges faced during execution of their *Final Year Project*.

Lastly, the paper outlines future work that aim to further improve the teaching of *Product Design and Development*, and to enhance design-build experience that integrates design thinking, chemical product design and relevant elements of the original institutional module, as well as to integrate product and process designs.

KEYWORDS

Chemical engineering, design-build experience, design thinking, chemical product design

INTRODUCTION

Final year project (FYP) has been the hallmark for the Diploma in Chemical Engineering at Singapore Polytechnic (SP). All graduating Year 3 students must complete a project as part of the course requirement. One of the major challenges we faced in the past years was the lack of framework on which the execution of FYP can be based. In CDIO parlance, both lecturers and students lacked skills in conceiving, designing, implementing and operating an engineering product or system by applying various chemical engineering principles learnt. There was no consistent approach that guides the project execution process and as a result approaches varied considerably from project to project depending on the supervisor.

Traditionally FYPs in chemical engineering are largely proposed by lecturers. When opportunities arise to collaborate with external research institutes, these initiatives (often referred as external projects) are incorporated as FYPs as well. More recently, the team introduced the so-called student-initiated projects, whereby students can suggest suitable topics where they would like to work on. This has limited success as students in general lacked the skills to conceive meaningful, executable projects, and lecturers also lacked the skills to coach them.

In January 2007, the Diploma in Chemical Engineering decided to adopt the CDIO Framework as the basis of its curriculum revamp, especially to improve the execution of our FYP in terms of students' ability to practice conceiving, designing, implementing and operating a product or systems. To better meet the needs of chemical engineering, we integrated the CDIO Framework into a new module on chemical product design entitled *Product Design and Development*, which was introduced into the Year 2 chemical engineering curriculum. The module was subscribed for the first time by our students in Academic Year 2009. At the time of this writing, one cohort of students (about 120) had completed the module. We hoped that with this module, more students will be able to generate new ideas, screen those ideas and select a promising one, propose viable solutions, and select an implementation solution to carry on in Year 3 as student-initiated projects.

An added "challenge" comes in the form of so-called institutional modules that are compulsory for all students regardless of what diploma program they chose to study. The objective of having institutional modules is to ensure that every full-time SP graduate has attained a minimum level of skill or ability in certain competencies deemed important by the institution. One of these institutional modules is *Innovation, Design and Enterprise in Action*, or *IDEA* in short. Using a fixed curriculum, the module is taught to all students from all diplomas in Year 1, with the main objective of developing in students an attitude for basic creativity, design literacy, innovation and enterprise, through an understanding of the design process. Through experiential project-based learning, students are required to question their preconceptions, see things from multiple perspectives, generate new ideas and make them work, develop visual and verbal presentation to sell their new ideas to others to create new uses and lifestyles. However, our students often failed to appreciate the teachings of this module, as the fixed curriculum bears no resemblance to their study in chemical engineering.

With the emergence of design thinking, we are now reviewing how to integrate it with the CDIO Framework to further strengthen the ability of our students to conceive useful products or experiences. This will be done by customizing the *IDEA* module to suit the needs of chemical engineering. A new module (tentatively entitled *Introduction to Chemical Product Design*) embracing design thinking, chemical product design and relevant elements of the original *IDEA* module will be created.

The aim is to provide a seamless coverage of skills in conceiving, designing, implementing and operating (abbreviated as C-D-I-O skills in this paper) an engineering system (product, solution) using chemical engineering principles, integrate with innovative user experience, across the three years of study, as shown in Figure 1. This approach is consistent with the model adopted to sustain the Diploma in Chemical Engineering curriculum revamp [1].

C - D - I - O Skills: C o n c e i v e - D e s i g n - I m p l e m e n t - O p e r a t e

Stage 1A	Stage 1B	Stage 2A	Stage 2B	Stage 3A	Stage 3B
Introduction to Chemical Engineering	N.A.	Engineering Mathematics IIA	Engineering Mathematics IIB	Process Control & Optimization	
Basic Mathematics	Engineering Mathematics I	Fluid Mechanics	Rotating Equipment	Separation Processes I	Separation Processes II
Analytical & Physical Chemistry	Inorganic & Organic Chemistry	Heat Transfer & Equipment	Chemical Reaction Engineering	Thermodynamics	
Materials in Practice	Pharmaceutical Microbiology	Process Instrumentation	Environmental Engineering	Project (CDIO DBE)	Project (CDIO DBE)
Chemical Process Principles & Simulation	Introduction to Chem Thermodynamics	Plant Safety & Loss Prevention	N.A.	Free Elective 1	Free Elective 3
N.A.	Intro to Chemical Product Design	Product Design and Development	Product Design and Development (cont'd)	Free Elective 2	Free Elective 4
Stakeholder Module No.1	Teamwork and Communication Toolbox	N.A.	Stakeholder Module No. 2	N.A.	Stakeholder Module No. 3
		Industrial Training Programme	Industrial Training Programme		

Figure 1. Integrating C-D-I-O Skills into 3-year chemical engineering program

THE EMERGENCE OF CHEMICAL PRODUCT ENGINEERING: A BRIEF REVIEW

Chemical engineering as a discipline on its own is relatively young, starting with the integration of industrial chemistry and physics into an engineering science [2]. As an engineering discipline, chemical engineering has constantly evolved to meet the demand of the chemical process industries [3], [4].

As we moved into the new millennium, the chemical process industries, which include the petroleum, fine chemicals, pharmaceuticals and health, cosmetics, household care, agro and food, environment and electronics sectors, have been facing dramatic social, economic and technical challenges, on a global and local scale. Globalization, advances in technology, concerns over the sustainability of natural resources, etc had lead to the creation of new industries where chemical engineers are wanted. Recent chemical engineering graduates now found employment in industries that did not exist 10-20 years ago or did not until recently discover the usefulness and relevance of chemical engineers in their profession [5]. New opportunities had opened up for chemical engineers in areas such as pharmaceuticals, biotechnology, nanotechnology, product development, and sustainable development [6].

In the field of chemical engineering, one often speaks of a new “paradigm of chemical engineering” when the profession responded to the various changes affecting it [7]. The idea of chemical product design as the “third paradigm” of chemical engineering was first suggested by Villermaux [8] and later popularized by Wei [9]. This is followed by a landmark publication of the first textbook specifically addressing chemical product design by Cussler and Moggridge [10]. Various other publications soon followed, see for example, Wei [11], and Wesselingh et al [12].

Recently Costa et al [13], proposed a structure for chemical product engineering, which encompasses chemical product design and its integration with process design using a multi-faceted approach as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Structure for chemical product engineering

The emergence of chemical product engineering means that today's chemical engineers must be educated differently. Villadsen [14] remarked that "...the direction of the education must be changed to put the product rather than the process into focus ...", adding that "... it would be a major mistake to exclude chemical engineers from their potential competitive advantage in chemical products due to inappropriate design of their curricula". Wintermantel [15] noted that "... the background knowledge that these chemical engineers need to have differs considerably in some ways from that of "classically" educated process engineers ..."

To be a chemical engineer of today means being involved in customer satisfaction, research, product development, process and manufacturing controls, and marketing [16]. For example, a chemical engineer may be a member of the original new concept team and stay with a product throughout the entire development cycle, throughout its service life and right through to material recycling. As noted by Bruin [17]: "Chemical engineers will be more and more involved in designing end-consumer products and suitable processes to manufacture them."

The teaching of chemical product design using chemical engineering principles is a relatively new concept for majority of chemical engineers. This is because these products, which include performance chemicals, pharmaceuticals, formulated products such as household, beauty or personal care products, and processed foods; have historically been the domain of chemists, material scientists and food technologists while chemical engineers focused on manufacturing processes [18].

The introduction of chemical product design had provided the much needed extra dimension in chemical engineering education to move it away from just chemical process design, where the distinction between product and process design was already made abundantly clear by Moggridge and Cussler [19]. The new paradigm now is that chemical engineers can have a significant role in the fashioning of the products themselves.

Related developments in green engineering, process intensification, micro-scale processing etc are all converging on chemical product engineering, along with more traditional chemical process design. Academic institutions around the world therefore made changes to their chemical engineering curriculum to introduce chemical product design. Being a new paradigm, chemical product engineering still faced various challenges as it is being integrated into chemical engineering curriculum [20], [21], [22]. Cussler and Wei [23] stressed that educational changes in this area will be evolutionary in nature rather than revolutionary as we expand our examples beyond those based on petrochemical feedstocks. Case studies have been developed as a means of providing chemical engineers with an awareness of issues such as product innovation, consumer demand and sustainability; see for example Ng et al [24], Bernado et al, [25], Farrell et al [26], Shaeiwitz and Turton [27].

CHEMICAL PRODUCT DESIGN FOR THE DIPLOMA IN CHEMICAL ENGINEERING

Here in Singapore Polytechnic, we recognized the changing landscape in chemical engineering education and decided to incorporate chemical product design into our curriculum. There had been a “missing link” between the *IDEA* module in Year 1 and *Final Year Project* in Year 3. As mentioned in the previous section, our students failed to appreciate the usefulness of the *IDEA* module, and certainly failed to apply its principles in the execution of their projects. A large part of the difficulty stems from the rigid nature of the *IDEA* curriculum that is not easily contextualized to the needs of chemical engineering. A one-size-fit-all *IDEA* module is clearly insufficient. To bridge the gap, we decided to introduce a new module in Year 2 in the existing curriculum that introduces students to the concepts of chemical product design.

We adopted the 4-step product design methodology for chemical engineering proposed by Cussler and Moggridge [10] that is already widely used in business development and manufacturing. In a nutshell, the procedure centred around the concepts of “needs”, “ideas”, “selection”, and “manufacture’ as follows:

1. Needs: What needs should the product fill?
2. Ideas: What different products could fill this need?
3. Selection: Which ideas are the most promising?
4. Manufacture: How can we make the product and test it critically?

In deciding to teach chemical product design at the diploma level, we are mindful of the need to manage the curriculum within the capability of the students. As noted by Costa et al [13], chemical product engineering is strongly dependent on a multi-scale perspective. The ultimate aim of the discipline is the translation of phenomenological laws and models, expressed by property, process and usage functions, into commercial product technology. Examples for chemical and bioprocess engineering as given by Charpentier [28] are shown in Figure 3.

Several authors had put forward suggested curriculum for the teaching of chemical product engineering, see for example Saraiva and Costa [29], Favre et al [30], Gomes [31], and Seider et al [32]. These are aimed at university undergraduate or Masters-level. However, as noted by Crawley et al [33], we need to adapt the CDIO approach to meet our own needs. At the diploma level, we recognized that there is not enough depth in terms of the fundamental sciences as the curriculum seek to balance the needs of the chemical industry for process technicians and our own graduates’ aspiration for further education.

Thus as far as the Diploma in Chemical Engineering is concerned, coverage of chemical product engineering is best carried out mainly at the meso-scale and micro-scale; where as fundamental research in product design and more in-depth technical coverage (for examples: property estimation, nano-scale characterization, computational fluid dynamics, systems modelling and non-linear programming, etc) are best left to the universities.

Figure 3. Scales and complexity levels in chemical and bioprocess engineering

The following sections discuss in detail the work done for the Year 2 module *Product Design and Development*, and briefly outlined the changes in Year 3 module *Final Year Project*.

Product Design and Development

We added a new module on chemical product design entitled *Product Design and Development* to the Year-2 curriculum with the primary aim of tying-in with our Year 1 *IDEA* module and Year 3 *Final Year Project* to provide a comprehensive coverage of skills in conceiving, designing, implementing, and operating an engineering product or system using chemical engineering principles; as shown in Figure 1. The stated module aims of the module *Product Design and Development* is stated below:

“To provide students with the essential skills and techniques in market research, idea generation and prototype development conducted at the conceptual phase of product design using chemical engineering principles.”

At the end of the module, students will be able to:

1. Identify and translate customer needs into preliminary product design specifications.
2. Use a range of creative thinking tools and techniques in generating ideas and solutions
3. Evaluate of ideas and solutions
4. Use system thinking in problem solving
5. Search intellectual property in product manufacture
6. Apply technical knowledge learnt to create a prototype

Students are also expected to use the knowledge learnt in the *IDEA* module during the ideation process. At the end of Year 2, the idea selected and possible solution proposed in the *Product Design and Development* module can be further refined and lead to the conception of a suitable product for subsequent design, implementation and operation in *Final Year Project* in Year 3.

The secondary purpose of the *Product Design and Development* module serves to reinforce the two design-build experiences (DBEs) introduced earlier (April 2008) as part of the launch of CDIO-enabled chemical engineering curriculum revamp: one basic-level DBE in Year 1 *Introduction to Chemical Engineering*, and another intermediate-level DBE in *Chemical Reaction Engineering*. In *Introduction to Chemical Engineering*, the DBE requires students to fabricate a DIY Water Filter Kit using a hollow-out plastic measuring cylinder. They are to select three out of four given materials (namely pebbles, corals, sand and crushed granite) for the filter media. They are also required to price their product, given basic costs of the raw materials. In the *Chemical Reaction Engineering* DBE, students are required to fabricate a simple chemical reactor using plastic tubings, to achieve a required production rate of a product of specified purity. They were given 3 tubes of different diameters, and hence need to make a trade-off between reactor diameter against reactor length, to achieve the same reaction conversion.

The *Product Design and Development* module is assessed fully based on in-course continuous assessments, as shown in Table 1. Detailed Guidance Notes for Students as well as comprehensive assessment criteria were also developed, and these are shown in Appendix 1.

Table 1
Assessment Scheme for *Product Design & Development* Module

Continuous Assessment	Means of Assessment	Weightage (%)
Product Design Assessment No. 1 – User Research	Mini Research Report Oral Presentation	15 15
Product Design Assessment 2 – Design and Development of a Prototype	Final Project Report Logbook Oral Presentation	40 10 20

At the point of this writing, we have completed a first year of teaching of *Product Design and Development*. A total of 60 projects from 20 groups were proposed in this module, where some of the more interesting ones are listed in Table 2. Students interested in furthering their work from the *Product Design and Development* module into Year 3 can submit their proposals for student-initiated projects and source for suitable lecturers to be their supervisors.

Final Year Project

All Year 3 students from the Diploma in Chemical Engineering need to complete a *Final Year Project* in order to graduate. This is essentially the capstone design-build experience project for our students. Prior to adoption of the CDIO framework, most if not all, projects are proposed solely by lecturers, or in collaboration with industrial sponsors.

Table 2
List of projects proposed by students from *Product Design & Development*

Eco Dance Floor	Fluorescent umbrella	Colour coating for spectacle lens
Self-cleaning table	Smokeless cigarettes	Massager backpack
Blue corn milk	Magical white board	Stainless shirt from carbon nanotubes
Generator bike	Scented medicated oil	Exotic fragrance shower gel
Flubber soap	Sweat-to-ester deodorant	Environmentally-friendly digestible chewing gum
Detergent stick	Waterproof spray plaster	Free-form earpiece
Ink evaporator	Anti-smoking perfume	Water plus fertilizer sprinkler
	Ash-less incense paper	

With the introduction of *Product Design and Development*, we hoped to have more students proposing their own projects in Year 3 by leveraging on the work done in the Year 2 *Product Design and Development* module.

We have 3 broad categories of projects: lecturer-proposed, industry-sponsored and student-initiated. Lecturer-proposed projects typically ranged widely from basic applied research to design and construction of pilot plants, covering areas in plant operation and optimization, occupational safety and health, alternative fuels, etc; reflecting the broad-based nature of our chemical engineering curriculum. In addition, with greater emphasis on the use of laptops at the institutional level and the availability of simple-to-use software have also encourage staffs to propose software-based final year student projects such as e-learning Flash animation packages, or computer-based optimization studies. Industry-sponsored projects tend to focus exclusively on fundamental research. With student-initiated projects, we naturally expect more chemical products to be coming out of the pipeline.

Although some of the learning outcomes for students undergoing the final year student projects can be argued to be generically the same, the current one-size-fits-all assessment system that we have had become cumbersome to use. To better reflect the nature of work carried out by students, it is important that they are assessed based on different criteria relevant to the nature of the project. We broadly grouped our final year projects into three different genres of final year projects: (1) Research-based project, (2) Engineering project, and (3) E-learning project. Details of the work done are covered in a separate paper [34].

EVALUATION: ISSUES AND CHALLENGES

Two surveys were carried out: one for Year 2 students and another for Year 3 students, specifically those who initiated their own projects. Survey questionnaire were use for all the Year 2 students taking the module *Product Design and Development*. The primary purpose is to obtain feedback on their learning experience, usefulness of various topics, and how they felt in continuing the work done in the module as their final year projects. The full findings of the Year 2 questionnaire survey will be presented elsewhere [35]. This paper focus on the main learning points gained pertaining to the “bridging” effort and main lessons learnt that allow us to further improve the teaching of the *Product Design and Development* module.

From the survey, the predominant view among students is that there is insufficient understanding of applicable chemical engineering principles after their Year 2 study, to comfortably forward their proposals as *Final Year Project* for Year 3. Students in general are also unsure what sort of experimentation work that can be carried out for their proposed chemical product. For example, a group may be interested in producing scented medicated oil, but was unsure the kind of experimentation required for product realization. Students also lacked skills in basic experiments such as organic synthesis and formulation. Although they had been encouraged to seek out lecturers to help them in defining the scope for possible *Final Year Project*, many are reluctant to do so. Among the reasons offered was that they are not aware of each lecturer's respective area of expertise, as they had not been taught by the lecturer. Hence they are rather apprehensive in approaching any lecturer out of fear of being turned away. Some students may also have some (often unjustified) preconceived notion about the "relative approachability" of various lecturers. Many students are also under the wrong impression that they need to produce a physical prototype, or even a working model! Some expressed concern over the consequence of a "poor" proposal on their overall grades.

Of those students who went ahead nonetheless, some of the reasons cited as their main motivating factor are: "chance to carry out something that they actually interested in", "need not be subjected to balloting process, in case we got project that we do not liked", "we want to be the one deciding what we wanted to do". At the point of the writing of this paper, at least two groups had proposed to start the student-initiated projects.

As for the Year 3 students, focus group discussion was used to obtain their feedback. A total of six project groups were involved. It is worthwhile to note that these students did not take the *Product Design and Development* module when they were in Year 2. When queried on the ideas for their Final Year Project proposal, these students reported that they do not use any particular strategies to generate new ideas, nor do they rigorously evaluate all possible solutions. These students used a fair amount of trial-and-error when carrying out their projects, trying out different parameters without a systematic way of designing their experimental tasks. While some groups gave due consideration to biodegradability or disposal of their designs at end-of-life, some have not gave such issues much thought. Most students also do not appear to give sufficient considerations to market or commercialize their products.

With the introduction of the *Product Design and Development* module, we hope to see the inadequacies found in the above Year 3 students be eliminated when these current Year 2 students moved into Year 3.

We find that by far the greatest challenge is in integrating chemical product design across the entire 3-year duration of the program. We plan to both backward and forward integrate the Year 2 *Product Design and Development* with Year 1 *IDEA* and Year 3 *Final Year Project*, as shown in Figure 1. At the point of this writing, responding to feedback from various diplomas about the inadequacy of the institutional *IDEA* module, SP management has permitted each diploma leeway in customizing the module to meet its respective domain-specific requirements. Tying together three modules seamlessly over three years is something that we had not attempted before, and we will be leveraging on some previous work by others from the literature, for example the LIPS Model from Linköping [33]. There will be new challenges on a wide variety of issues pertaining to student progression in the program, such as failure in one or more core modules, removal from program due to poor results, etc that may affect the composition of the project team. These are very real issues that we will have to tackle.

Another challenge is to overcome the mindset of many lecturers. We believed that there are still resistances to teaching chemical product design – that many lecturers still have a preference for easily quantifiable and analytical problems in core chemical engineering modules. Except for a handful of lecturers who are involved in the teaching of *IDEA* and *Product Design and Development*, the rest are all trained in the “traditional” chemical engineering that focuses on process design rather than product design. Although basic training in chemical product design had been conducted, it is a fact that these lecturers lacked real-world experience in this area; and thus are uncomfortable in dealing with the uncertain outcomes inherent in product design and development.

FUTURE PLANS

We acknowledged that “delays” in knowledge acquisition is an inevitable outcome of a modular way of teaching. To address this, we would emphasize greater independent learning on the part of the students, to pick up new concepts that are not yet taught in class. On our part, we must make more resources available to students. To this end, we must first review our student module registration process. Currently students can only view online the materials for the modules for which they are registered, i.e. students registered for Year 2 Semester 1 can only view materials for the modules in Year 2 Semester 1. By removing such restriction, we can make more resources available to students at any time, making it easier for students to acquire the necessary knowledge needed for the study of *Product Design and Development*.

To reinforce the above, we also plan to revise the *Product Design and Development* module to introduce more examples on application of various chemical engineering principles such as fluid mechanics, heat transfer, etc in product design and development. This can be achieved by having more tutorial questions on chemical product design embedded in the relevant core chemical engineering modules. Promoting such greater curriculum integration can also help students better understand the connections between different chemical engineering concepts and principles taught in separate modules, which is important in chemical product design.

We are now in the process of studying the possibility of introducing various experiments on basic chemical engineering sciences such as mixing, colloid formation, surface tension measurement, viscosity modification, etc which is currently missing from our laboratory sessions. These, coupled with the teaching of design of experiments that we will introduce into the revised *Product Design and Development* module, will provide students with hands-on experience in conducting experimental work for their proposed chemical products, instead of simply doing so by trial-and-error.

As for the revision of *IDEA* module, we have started development work to introduce the concept of chemical product pyramid introduced by Costa et al [13]. The revision will also include using design thinking to support the ideation process (i.e. the “conceive” component of C-D-I-O skills) in chemical product design. Design thinking is a new approach (popularized by IDEO CEO Tim Brown) that is currently taking the business world by storm. The planned roll out of the revised *IDEA* module is Academic Year 2011. This will provide us with enough time to build up faculty competence in design thinking, as well as making other structural changes to our diploma programs for example, in allocating common timeslot for students from different diplomas across several schools to come together and work together.

Work is also in progress to provide more training to our lecturers, via industrial attachment to relevant companies such as Philips or 3M; as well as in-house design thinking workshops. We hoped that more exposure to real-world chemical product design work will help to encourage more buy-in to overcome the problem of lack of confidence on the part of many lecturers.

On the intermediate term, we will be looking into the introduction of a new elective module that teaches more “exotic” unit operations such as emulsification, spray cooling, extrusion, coating and granulation, which are more relevant to product design and development. Over the longer term, the team will also study how to integrate chemical product engineering with the “traditional” chemical process design. Amundson [36] has long highlighted the need to integrate product design with process design, and that chemical engineering will serve as the “interfacial discipline” of the future, bridging science and engineering in the multi-disciplinary environments where new technologies will be brought into being. Several literatures have been published in recent years that address this issue [37], [38], [39].

As with current practice, we will continue to engage students as co-participants in our journey to revamp the Diploma in Chemical Engineering curriculum. These students had served as a rich source of information for improving our past revamps efforts. In addition, we will also come up with fresh surveys to follow-up with these students after their graduation from Singapore Polytechnic.

CONCLUSIONS

Compared to other engineering disciplines, chemical engineering is a late-comer in terms of applying its basic principles in product design and development. We are now playing catch-up in responding to changing landscape that is happening globally, both at the workplace and in the academia. The Institution of Chemical Engineers, UK noted that still a lot of work has to be done to develop a generally applicable chemical product design and engineering framework [40]. Since the publication of the 4-step process of Cussler and Moggridge [10], many variations has been introduced, see for example Gomes [31], Kavanagh and Lant [41]. The notion of chemical product design has already been enlarged to be part of chemical product engineering [13]. And recently Costa et al [42] reported that a pedagogic research project, entitled “Developing Chemical Product Engineering Education for the 21st Century” has been initiated. Many other changes in chemical product engineering are still taking place.

Voncken et al [43] noted that innovation is a key factor in survival for companies that produce specialty chemical products. A new paradigm that is sweeping across the design world is that of design thinking. By integrating design thinking into chemical product engineering, we hope to have a complete framework on which to revise our curriculum that prepares our graduates for the new environment.

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Biographical Information

Sin-Moh Cheah is a chemical engineer turned academic. His current portfolio includes course promotion and outreach, as well as current student and alumni relations. His scholarly interests are curriculum re-design and program evaluation. He has lectured on various topics including chemical engineering principles, separation processes, heat transfer and equipment, and chemical reaction engineering. He held various positions in Mobil Oil Singapore Pte Ltd (now part of ExxonMobil) prior to joining Singapore Polytechnic.

Huiting Ng is a lecturer in the Diploma in Chemical Engineering and a Teacher Advisor for the diploma's Student Chapter. She has a keen interest in education pedagogy and is currently one of the few faculties with experience in design thinking. She also has a strongly interest in water-related projects. Her current works include applying the reflux-recycle concept from distillation to reverse osmosis; and the development of a novel solar-powered ambient water generator.

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Appendix 1 *Product Design & Development* Module

Guidance Notes for Students

Product Design Assessment No.1 (User Research)

In this team assignment, you are required to observe and find out from your daily lives bug lists of problems that you have to face everyday which are preferably chemical in nature, and come up with some innovative solutions to the top three short-listed problems. You can also revisit the laboratories and practical workshops where you had attended and are attending and identify the problems you observed. You must be able to identify the product/design attributes on how they solve your stipulated problem, and enhancements needed to satisfy the functional (and marketing, if any) requirements.

The examples of chemical and chemical related industries you may want to explore include, but are not limited, to the following areas.

Biochemical	Petroleum & Oil Refining
Biotechnology (Biomedical & Healthcare)	Pharmaceuticals
Chemicals	Plastics & Polymers
Cosmetics	Process Control & Instrumentation
Environment and Energy	Process Engineering
Fertilizers	Semiconductors & Electronics
Food and Beverages	Ultra-pure Water
Energy & Fuels	Wastewater Treatment
Petrochemicals	Specialty Chemicals

To do this assignment, you will have to:

- identify the bugs or problems in the daily lives or in the laboratories / workshops / industries which are preferably chemical in nature
- analyse the customer needs in these problems via end-user surveys and questionnaires
- analyse the chemical and design components of a product
- apply the creative problem solving process to generate new products
- produce design specifications of possible new products for the industry

Product Design Assessment No.2 (Design and Development of a Prototype)

To do this assignment, you will have to:

- refine the solution you proposed earlier based on your latest research, technical and fundamental knowledge, feedback and comments from your classmates and lecturers during the Question and Answer session in Assessment No.1
- propose appropriate marketing strategies
- create a prototype using low cost materials

Assessment Criteria

Mini Research Report (marks allocation in brackets)

1. Effective identification / interpretation of customer needs (20%)
 - Effective use of a range of critical thinking skills (e.g. analysis, comparison and contrast, inference and interpretation, evaluation)

- Effective identification of opportunities/problems via market-research surveys, end-user surveys, questionnaires etc to collate feedback
 - Conversion of the customer needs to initial specifications qualitatively/quantitatively
2. Technical knowledge and reasoning applied in problem solving (20%)
 - Effective use of domain knowledge and technical facts in proposed solution
 - Research or literature survey conducted on the specific problem and proposed solution
 3. Creativity and innovation in problem solving (20%)
 - Effective use of a range of critical thinking skills (e.g. analysis, comparison and contrast, inference and interpretation, evaluation)
 - Effective use of creative thinking tools and techniques
 - Identify contradictory perspectives and underlying assumptions
 4. Teamwork (20%)
 - Effective identification of team roles after analysing each member's strength and weakness
 - Good management of time and resources in the whole assignment
 5. Preliminary Work (20%)
 - Carry out sufficient literature search to meet the scope of the project
 - Plan to organize work schedule logically and independently

Final Project Report (marks allocation in brackets)

1. Application of technical knowledge & reasoning to refine the solution (40%)
 - Able to address key issues raised from your classmates and lecturers
 - Apply the technical knowledge and reasoning to refine the design
 - Effective use of creative thinking tools and techniques
2. Effectiveness of marketing approach of the product (20%)
 - Analysis on how this product is different from the existing similar products in the market (if any)
 - Proposal on how to market this innovative product or possible avenue for enterprise
3. Creation of prototype (40%)
 - Effective use of design of experiments to identify the optimum specification of the product or prototype
 - Identification of opportunities for further work at the Final Year Project level

Oral Presentation

The work produced by the team should be presented as an organized presentation. The structure and presentation must clearly show the development of your thinking and acquisition of knowledge to the production of the initial design. You must include appropriate diagrams and products, e.g. models, to illustrate the important stages of the design process. It is essential that all members contribute to the presentation in approximately equal parts. The team will be expected to answer questions posed by assessing lecturers and your classmates.

1. Design and deliver presentation well in proper and formal English
2. Speak clearly and coherently
3. Ask and answer questions effectively
4. Exhibits technical competency and know-how in the project